

A new genus of Parreysiinae Henderson, 1935 from Yunnan, China (Bivalvia: Unionidae)

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Abstract. A new genus of freshwater mussel, *Chenunionetta* n. gen., is described from Yunnan, China. It is distinguished from other genera of Indochinellini by its irregularly elongate triangular shell, an elongate, narrow, and relatively pointed posterior end, a weak ridge near the posterodorsal margin, and a smooth transition between the dorsal and posterior margins.

Key words. Freshwater molluscs, new taxon, taxonomy, *Unionetta xishuangbannaensis*

Introduction

The subfamily Parreysiinae Henderson, 1935 is widely distributed across tropical Asia and Africa and is highly diverse (Graf & Cummings, 2026; MolluscaBase eds., 2026). Compared with other subfamilies of Unionidae Rafinesque, 1820, however, Parreysiinae remains comparatively understudied, with only limited molecular phylogenetic evidence available (Bolotov *et al.*, 2018, 2020, 2024; Pfeiffer *et al.*, 2018; Graf & Cummings, 2026). Taxonomic uncertainty persists in many genera within this subfamily, highlighting the need for further systematic revision (Bolotov *et al.*, 2018; Pfeiffer *et al.*, 2018; Graf & Cummings, 2026).

Unionetta xishuangbannaensis Chen *et al.*, 2026, recently described from Yunnan, is currently the only known representative of Parreysiinae from China (Chen *et al.*, 2026). In the present study, we establish a new genus to accommodate *U. xishuangbannaensis*, thereby preserving the monophyly of *Unionetta* Haas, 1955.

Systematics

Family **Unionidae** Rafinesque, 1820

Subfamily **Parreysiinae** Henderson, 1935

Tribe **Indochinellini** Bolotov, Pfeiffer, Vikhrev & Konopleva in Bolotov *et al.*, 2018

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<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:B2433AD4-A828-445C-80EC-75C4DE05ADB0>

Genus *Chenunionetta* n. gen.

陈珠蚌属 (Pinyin: chén zhū bàng shǔ)

Type species. *Unionetta xishuangbannaensis* Chen, Dai, Zheng, Ouyang & Wu, 2026.

Diagnosis. An Indochinellini genus characterised by an irregularly elongate triangular shell, an elongate, narrow, and relatively pointed posterior end, a weak ridge near the posterodorsal margin, and a smooth transition between the dorsal and posterior margins.

Etymology. The genus is named in honour of Dr Zhong-Guang Chen (陈重光), who discovered the type species, and is combined with the generic name *Unionetta*.

Distribution. China: Yunnan; Cambodia; possibly Laos. In China, the new genus is known only from the Menglun section of the Luosuo River, a tributary of the Lancang River, and has not been recorded from either upstream or downstream reaches (Chen *et al.*, 2026).

Remarks. Molecular phylogenetic analyses by Pfeiffer *et al.* (2018) and Chen *et al.* (2026) consistently indicate that the new genus and *Unionetta* do not form a monophyletic group. Although Chen *et al.* (2026) recommended refraining from erecting a new genus because several genera within Indochinellini are widely non-monophyletic, we consider the establishment of a new genus necessary to preserve the monophyly of *Unionetta*.

The new genus is currently monotypic. Pfeiffer *et al.* (2018) reported an unidentified species from northern Cambodia that belongs to this lineage. From biogeographic and morphological perspectives, *Unio molleuri* Morlet, 1891, currently treated as a junior synonym of *Unionetta fabagina* (Deshayes in Deshayes and Jullien, 1876) and distributed in Laos, may also be attributable to the new genus. It is possible that *U. molleuri* corresponds to the unidentified species reported by Pfeiffer *et al.* (2018). Pending the collection and examination of topotypic material, we refrain from revalidating this taxon or transferring it to the new genus.

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References

- Bolotov, I. N., Konopleva, E. S., Vikhrev, I. V., Gofarov, M. Y., Lopes-Lima, M., Bogan, A. E., Lunn, Z., Chan, N., Win, T., Aksenova, O. V., Tomilova, A. A., Tanmuangpak, K., Tumpeesuwan, S., Kondakov, A. V. (2020) New freshwater mussel taxa discoveries clarify biogeographic division of Southeast Asia. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1): 6616
- Bolotov, I. N., Pfeiffer, J. M., Konopleva, E. S., Vikhrev, I. V., Kondakov, A. V., Aksenova, O. V., Gofarov, M. Y., Tumpeesuwan, S. & Win, T. (2018) A new genus and tribe of freshwater mussel (Unionidae) from Southeast Asia. *Scientific Reports*, 8: 10030.
- Bolotov, I. N., Sonowal, J., Kardong, D., Pasupuleti, R., Subba Rao, N. V., Unnikrishnan, S. K., Gofarov, M. Y., Kondakov, A. V., Konopleva, E. S., Lyubas, A. A., Vikhrev, I. V. (2024) Discovery of an endemism hotspot of freshwater mussels (Bivalvia: Unionidae) in Assam, with a description of two new genera. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 202(4): zlae052.
- Chen, Z.-G., Dai, Y.-T., Zheng, H., Ouyang, S., Wu, X.-P. (2026) *Unionetta xishuangbannaensis* n. sp. is the only representative of Parreysiinae Henderson, 1935 (Bivalvia: Unionidae) in China: evidence from molecular phylogeny and morphology. *Cathaica*, 2(5): 53–61.

- Deshayes, G. P. & Jullien, J. (1876) Mémoire sur les mollusques nouveaux du Cambodge envoyés au Muséum par M. le docteur Jullien. *Bulletin des Nouvelles Archives du Muséum*, 10: 115–163, 4 pls.
- Graf, D. L. & Cummings, K. S. (2026) The MUSSEL Project. Available from: <https://musselpdb.org> (2026-05-06).
- Haas, F. (1955) *Unionella* Haas 1913, vorweggenommen durch *Unionella* Etheridge 1888. *Archiv für Molluskenkunde*, 84: 212.
- Henderson, J. (1935) Fossil non-marine Mollusca of North America. *Geological Society of America Special Papers*, 3: 1–313.
- MolluscaBase eds. (2026) MolluscaBase. Available from: <https://www.molluscabase.org> (2026-05-06).
- Morlet, L. (1891) Contribution à la faune malacologique de l'Indo-Chine. *Journal de Conchyliologie*, 39: 230–254.
- Pfeiffer, J. M., Graf, D. L., Cummings, K. S. & Page, L. M. (2018) Molecular phylogeny and taxonomic revision of two enigmatic freshwater mussel genera (Bivalvia: Unionidae incertae sedis: Harmandia and Unionetta) reveals a diverse clade of Southeast Asian Parreysiinae. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 84(4): 1–13.
- Rafinesque, C. S. (1820) Monographie des coquilles bivalves et fluviatiles de la Rivière Ohio, contenant douze genres et soixante-huit espèces. *Annales Générales des Sciences Physiques*, 5(5): 287–322, pls 80–82.

云南雕刻蚌亚科（双壳纲：蚌科）一新属

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摘 要

本文描述了产自云南的河蚌新属：陈珠蚌属 *Chenunionetta* **n. gen.**。该属可依据以下特征与同族其他属区分：贝壳延长，不规则的三角形，具延长、狭窄且相对较尖的后部，背缘后部具一弱脊，且背缘与后缘平滑过渡。印支蚌族各属普遍非单系群，有待开展进一步的系统

关键词：淡水贝类，新阶元，分类学，版纳小珠蚌